

IMPROVED ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF CARBON NANOTUBE MAT COMPOSITE PREPARED BY IN-SITU POLYMERIZATION

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1 Introduction

Since Iijima's discovery of CNTs [1], numerous studies have been conducted related to the development of CNT composite materials due to their superior properties. CNT composites have been developed to exploit the superior properties of the CNTs in a laboratory setting, but they have not yet proved commercially viable due to difficulties in mass production [2]. An excellent dispersion of CNTs, which is easily managed in laboratory experiments, is difficult to mass produce manufacturing CNT composites with improved mechanical and electrical properties [3]. The mass production of CNT composites with enhanced thermal properties is also difficult due to the imperfect contact among the CNTs in the composites [4,5]. A continuous CNT mat, which can prevent both the poor dispersion of the CNTs and the imperfect contact among the CNTs in the composites, has been studied to overcome the problems of mass producing CNT composites.

Continuous CNT mats are commonly produced by vacuum filtration of a dispersed CNT suspension and can be used for diverse applications such as actuators [6], electrodes [7], gas separators [8], and sensors [9], etc. Highly conductive composites with excellent mechanical properties can be fabricated using a continuous CNT mat filler because the CNTs in the CNT mat composites are uniformly dispersed and are in direct contact. Many researchers have reported the production of CNT mat composites through the use of various processes such as electrospinning [10], hot compression [11], intercalation [12,13], and through-thickness infiltration [14,15] with various polymer resins such as epoxy [14,16], polycarbonate [15,17], polyether-ether-ketone [10], polystyrene and polyvinyl alcohol [12,13]. The mechanical, electrical, and thermal properties of the

CNT mat composites depend on the degree of impregnation, the quality of the polymer resin, the content of the CNT mat, the properties of the interface between the CNT mat and the polymer resin, and characteristics of the CNT mat [18].

Thermoset CNT mat composites impregnated with a low-viscosity epoxy resin are commonly used because they eliminate the processing problems that arise from the nano structure and properties of the CNT mat, which hinder fabrication of thermoset CNT mat composite. The advantages of thermoset CNT mat composites include heat resistance and high-temperature mechanical properties. However, weaknesses exist such as non-recyclability of the products, low productivity due to a long curing process and difficulty in preparing complex products. Although recyclable thermoplastic CNT mat composites can be easily and rapidly manufactured using extrusion and injection molding, the CNT content in the mat composites is limited due to the low processability and high viscosity of the thermoplastic resins. This study reports a fabrication method to enhance the processability of a thermoplastic CNT mat composite developed using in-situ polymerizable low-viscosity CBT oligomers. In addition, the processing and structure property relationships of the prepared CNT mat composites were investigated.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

A CNT mat (Nanocomp Technologies Inc., Merrimack, NH, USA) and CBT (CBT 160, Cyclics Co., Schenectady, NY, USA) were used as the incorporated filler and polymer matrix, respectively, in the preparation of a thermoplastic CNT mat composite with improved properties. Individual

multi-walled CNTs (MWCNTs) with lengths of approximately 1 mm were grown using a typical chemical vapor deposition method. The MWCNTs were loosely collected by a rolling conveyor system and pressed into a dense mat-like structure [19]. The density of the CNT mat was approximately 0.25 g/cm³, and its free-volume fraction and thickness were approximately 86 % and 65 μm, respectively [20]. The large free-volume fraction enhanced the wettability of the CNT mat with the polymer matrix. The CBT 160 resin was a mixture of CBT powder and a polymerization catalyst. The CBT oligomer mixture consisted of butylene groups that varied in number from two to seven and resulted in a melting range of 130 to 150 °C with a low melt viscosity of approximately 20 cps. At temperatures above 160 °C, an entropically driven ring-opening polymerization occurred in the cyclic oligoesters, and the completely polymerized oligoesters were converted into pCBT with a structure that resembled poly(butylene terephthalate). The density of the pCBT was 1.3 g/cm³, and the CBT 160 resin was dried overnight at 110 °C to remove any moisture that could interfere with the polymerization [21].

2.2 Composite Preparation

A fixed quantity of CBT 160 powder was scattered onto a stainless steel mold, and the CNT mat was placed onto the scattered powder. A second fixed quantity of CBT 160 powder was scattered onto the CNT mat, and the stacked material was compressed with a heating press (D3P-20J, Dae Heung Science, In-Chon, Korea) under various pressing conditions to investigate the processing conditions, and structure property relations of the prepared CNT mat composites. The processing conditions are summarized in Table 1.

2.3 Electrical Conductivity

The four-probe method, according to ASTM D 257 (FPP-RS8, DASOL ENG, Cheong-Ju, Korea), was used to evaluate the electrical conductivity of the CNT mat composites under ambient conditions. A voltage drop of 500 V was applied between the center and the boundary of a sample, and the resistivity of the sample was obtained by measuring the output current. Electrical resistivity was calculated using the following equation [22]:

$$R = \frac{\Delta V wt}{iL} \quad (1)$$

in which R is the electrical resistivity, ΔV is the voltage drop over a distance of 6 mm, w is the width, t is the thickness, i is the current and L is the length. The electrical conductivity was calculated by taking the inverse of the resistivity and is given in units of Sm^{-1} .

2.4 Molecular Weight and Degree of Conversion

Gel permeation chromatography (GPC, HLC-8320 GPC EcoSEC, Tosoh Co., Tokyo, Japan) was used to evaluate the rate of conversion from CBT to pCBT. The measurements were conducted with a solvent mixture of chloroform and hexafluoro-2-isopropanol at a weight ratio was 98/2 and a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min at 20 °C. Two Waters PL HFIP-gel columns were utilized, and the chromatograph was connected to a Waters 484 UV detector working at 254 nm. A universal calibration was carried out using various polystyrene standards to relate the retention time to the molecular weight. Samples were prepared by dissolving 2 mg of resin in 80 μL of HFIP. The HFIP solution was then diluted with 4 mL of chloroform after total dissolution of the resin. The conversion rate was obtained based on the GPC measurements by comparing the quantity of oligomers remaining to the quantity of polymers according to Eq. (2):

$$\alpha = 1 - \frac{A_{oil}}{A_{tot}} \quad (2)$$

in which A_{oil} is the area under the oligomer peaks in the retention time curve and A_{tot} is the total area under the retention time curve.

2.5 Morphology

Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, JSM-6701F, JEOL USA Inc., Peabody, MA, USA) was used to observe the morphology of the CNT mat composite surfaces. The surfaces of the composites were coated with platinum using a sputter coating machine (Ion Sputter E-1030, Hitachi High Technologies Corp., Japan) under vacuum for 200 sec and observed via SEM at 15.0 kV.

2.6 Weight Fraction

Thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA, Q50, TA Instrument, New Castle, DE, USA) was used to determine the weight fraction of the incorporated CNT mat in the CNT mat composites under a nitrogen atmosphere over a temperature range of 40 to 900 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

2.7 Thermal Diffusivity

A thermowave analyzer (BETHEL Co., Ltd, Ibaraki, Japan) was used to measure thermal diffusivity of the CNT mat composites in both the in- and out-of-plane directions. The sample surface was irradiated with a laser, $P_0 e^{i\omega t}$, and found to have a thermal diffusivity of α . The temperature at the surface was $T_{ac} = T_0 e^{i\omega t}$, and the temperature diffusion was calculated as follows:

$$T_{ac} = \frac{P_0}{4\pi\alpha r c} \cdot e^{-kr+i(\omega t-kr)} \quad (3)$$

in which c is the heat capacity, r is distance from the heat source, and k is

$$k = \sqrt{\frac{\omega}{2\alpha}} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi f}{\delta}} = \frac{1}{\mu} \quad (4)$$

in which μ is the thermal diffusion length. Therefore, the phase lag could be derived as follows:

$$\theta = -\sqrt{\frac{\pi f}{\alpha}} \cdot r \quad (5)$$

The distance-variation and frequency-variation methods were used to measure the in-plane and out-of-plane thermal diffusivity of the CNT mat composites, respectively.

2.8 Crystalline Structure

Wide-angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD) measurements were performed to investigate the crystalline structure of the CBT and pCBT resins using an X-ray diffractometer (M18XHF-SRA, MAC Science Co., Tokyo, Japan) with Ni-filtered Cu K α X-rays ($\lambda = 0.1542\text{nm}$), and the diffraction intensity was recorded via continuous scanning at a rate of $0.02^\circ \text{ s}^{-1}$ over the range of $10^\circ < 2\theta < 40^\circ$ (θ = the Bragg angle).

2.9 Mechanical Properties

Tensile tests were performed according to ASTM D 882 [23] with a universal testing machine (Instron 5567A, Instron Co., Norwood, MA, USA). The specimen dimensions were 25 mm (L) \times 2.5 mm (W), and the gage length was 15 mm. The samples

were affixed to a paper-board frame and the sides of the frame were attached to the tensile test machine to protect the samples and to ensure proper alignment during the tests.

3 Results and Discussion

The electrical conductivity measured using the four-probe method depends largely on the resistance and thickness of the sample; therefore, the electrical properties of the CNT mat composites are summarized in Table 1 in terms of resistance, thickness and conductivity. The electrical conductivity was enhanced by increasing the compression pressure and a relatively large improvement was observed in the CNT mat composites prepared under low compression pressures. Table 1 provides confirmation that the large improvement was due to the considerable reduction in resistance of the CNT mat composites prepared under compression pressures of 0.5, 9 and 18 MPa. A relatively small improvement was observed for the CNT mat composites prepared under high compression pressures due to the reduction in thickness of the CNT mat composites prepared under compression pressures of 18, 27 and 36 MPa. A large difference was noted in the electrical conductivities of the CNT mat composites prepared under 36 MPa at 250 °C for 2 min and under 36 MPa at 190 °C for 40 min. The electrical conductivity of the quenched composites prepared under 36 MPa at 250 °C for 2 min was much higher than that of the composites cooled by air convection. A CBT oligomer resin was polymerized at a temperature above 160 °C and was converted into pCBT. Because the conversion rate from CBT to pCBT can significantly affect the properties of a composite, one must measure the conversion rate from CBT to pCBT with respect to the processing temperature. The conversion rate could not be evaluated using differential scanning calorimetry because the polymerization of the oligomer resin was an entropically driven non-exothermic reaction. Hence, the conversion rate was determined via GPC, a method used to measure the molecular weight of organic materials. The evaluated temperature range was limited between 160 to 250 °C because polymerization did not occur at temperatures below 160 °C, and the polymerization was too rapid at

temperatures higher than 250 °C, resulting in non-uniform and poor-quality specimens. Most of the oligomers were considered to be converted into polymers at 250 °C after 2 min and at 190 °C after 40 min, respectively. Thus, a long processing or cooling time adversely affected the electrical conductivity of the CNT mat composite as confirmed by the electrical conductivity of the composites prepared under applied pressure of 36 MPa at 250 °C for 2 min, which exhibited excellent results compared with a recently reported reference [18].

The surface morphology of the CNT mat composites was observed via SEM to investigate the significant reduction in the resistance of the composites. No CNTs were observed on the surface of the CNT mat composite prepared under a compression pressure of 0.5 MPa, whereas part of the continuous CNT mat was evident on the surface of the CNT mat composites prepared under compression pressures of 9, 18, 27 and 36 MPa. The CNTs were not fully connected when prepared under compression pressure of 9 MPa, but were fully connected in the CNT mat composites prepared under compression pressures of 18, 27 and 36 MPa. Given the resistance of the CNT mat composites in Table 1, direct contact between the four probes and the surface of the fully contacted quenched CNT mat composites prepared at 250 °C over 2 min, yielded resistances of 2.0~2.1 Ω. Therefore, the considerable decrease in the resistance of the CNT mat composites prepared under compression pressures of 0.5, 9 and 18 MPa was due to the development of fully connected CNTs on the surface of the CNT mat composites.

Because the weight fraction of the CNT mat in the CNT mat composites was affected by the compression pressure, and because it can influence the electrical conductivity of the CNT mat composite, the weight fraction was analyzed using TGA. The weight residue with respect to the temperature of the CNT mat composites is shown. As expected, the weight fraction increased with increasing compression pressure. Therefore, the differences in the electrical conductivities of the CNT mat composites prepared under compression pressures of 18, 27 and 36 MPa were attributed to the reduction in the thickness of the composites that occurred with the decrease in the pCBT fraction as the compression pressure increased. The

considerable reduction in the electrical conductivity of the CNT mat composites prepared under long processing or cooling times can be explained by the morphology results shown. The electrical conductivity was affected by the increase in sheet resistance caused by the morphology and the thickness of the composite specimens due to extended impregnation times for the matrix.

The thermal conductivities of the CNT mat and CNT mat composites are shown. A noticeable anisotropy occurred between the thermal conductivities in the in-plane and out-of-plane directions. The thermal conductivity of the CNT mat in the in-plane direction was 10,000 times larger than that in the out-of-plane direction. In the case of the composites, the anisotropy of the thermal conductivity was between 10 and 100 times. The thermal conductivity of the composites in the out-of-plane direction was not significantly affected by the processing conditions, and, as with the electrical conductivity, the in-plane direction was improved by increasing the compression pressure. This result indicated that the excellent thermal conductivity in the in-plane direction of the CNT mat composites prepared under high compression pressure could be attributed to the improved phonon transfer in the continuously connected CNT mat due to the alignment caused by the high compression pressure. Heat transfer in CNT composites is known to progress through phonon transfer; a previous study reported that heat was transported along the CNTs in CNT composites utilizing their high aspect ratio, and was exchanged at the nanotube tips [24]. The thermal diffusivity of the pristine CNT mat in the in-plane direction was between that of silver and copper. The thermal diffusivity in the in-plane direction of the CNT mat composites prepared under a compression of 36 MPa at 250 °C for 2 min was greater than that of alumina, which is a ceramic material. This historic result was achieved by the continuously and completely connected CNTs in the incorporated CNT mat. Previous studies [4,25] reported that the disappointing thermal conductivity in the CNT composites could be due to high contact resistance caused by the small contact area or incomplete contact between the CNTs.

As with the electrical conductivity, a substantial reduction in the in-plane thermal diffusivity of the CNT mat composites occurred with long processing

or cooling times though the development of a crystalline polymer structure is generally believed to have a positive effect on phonon transfer and the crystalline structure of the composite specimens prepared under long processing or cooling times was much more developed. Chen et al. [26] insisted that the phonon transfer in CNT composites progresses through the three-dimensionally thermally conductive pathways developed by the CNT fillers because the movement of phonons from the CNTs to the polymer matrix is limited due to the large interfacial resistance between the CNTs and the matrix. These results implied that the reduction in the in-plane thermal diffusivity of the composites prepared under long molding and cooling times could be attributed to the alignment of the CNT mat incorporated into the composites in the in-plane direction, which was randomized by heat. The alignment of the CNT mat in the composites was more important in determining the in-plane thermal diffusivity of the composites than the development of crystalline structure of the polymer matrix.

The mechanical properties of the CNT mat composites is shown with respect to the processing conditions. As the processing pressure increased, the tensile strength and modulus gradually increased until becoming saturated at compression pressures above 27 MPa. As with the electrical conductivity and thermal diffusivity, longer processing and cooling times adversely affected the mechanical properties. Because crystallization of the polymer matrix generally improves the mechanical properties of a composites, a reduction in the mechanical properties of the composites prepared under long molding and cooling times could be attributed to the alignment of the CNT mat incorporated into the composites in the in-plane direction, which was randomized by heat. Additionally, the alignment of the CNT mat in the composites was more important in determining the mechanical properties of the composites than the development of crystalline structure of the polymer matrix. From these results, the optimum processing conditions, to obtain excellent electrical, thermal and mechanical properties in the CNT mat composites, involved the combination of high compression pressure, short processing time and quenching to induce an alignment of the CNT mat in the in-plane direction of the composites.

4 Conclusion

In- situ polymerizable and low-viscosity CBT oligomers were used to enhance the processability of a thermoplastic CNT mat composite and the processing, and structure property relations of the prepared CNT mat composites were investigated. The electrical conductivity was enhanced by increasing the compression pressure, and relatively large and small improvements were observed for CNT mat composites prepared under low and high compression pressures, respectively. The considerable decrease in resistance for the CNT mat composites prepared under low compression pressures of 0.5, 9 and 18 MPa was due to the development of fully contacted CNTs on the surface of the CNT mat composites. The differences in the electrical conductivities of the CNT mat composites prepared under high compression pressures of 18, 27 and 36 MPa were attributed to the fact that the thickness of the composites was reduced by decreasing the pCBT fraction in the composites with increasing compression pressure. The considerable reduction in the electrical conductivity of the CNT mat composites prepared under long processing or cooling times can be explained by the increase in sheet resistance caused by the morphology and the increase in thickness caused by the longer impregnation time of the matrix. The excellent thermal conductivity of the CNT mat composites prepared under high compression pressure in the in-plane direction was attributed to improved phonon transfer in the continuously connected alignment of the CNT mat. The incorporation of continuously and completely connected CNTs in the CNT mat give the composites prepared under a compression of 36 MPa at 250 °C and 2 min a thermal diffusivity in the in-plane direction that is larger than that of alumina, a ceramic material. The reduction of the in-plane thermal diffusivity in the composites prepared using extended molding and cooling times could be attributed to the alignment of the incorporated CNT mat inside the composites in the in-plane direction that was randomized with heat. The alignment of the CNT mat in the composites was a more important physical parameter than the development of crystalline structure of the polymer matrix in determining the in-plane thermal diffusivity of the composites. The tensile strength and modulus of the composites increased gradually as the processing

pressure increased and became saturated under compression pressures above 27 MPa. As, with the thermal diffusivity, extended processing and cooling times had an adverse effect on the mechanical properties. The optimum processing conditions to achieve excellent electrical, thermal and mechanical properties of the CNT mat composites involved the combination of high compression pressure, short processing time and quenching, which induced an alignment of the CNT mat in the in-plane direction of the composites.

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Sample	Mold temperature (°C)	Compression time (min)	Compression pressure (MPa)	Cooling	Resistance (Ω /square)	Thickness (μ m)	Resistivity (Ω ·m)	Conductivity (S/m)
CNT mat			-		1.0	65	0.000065	15384.6
CCMC0.5			0.5		9.2	161	0.0014812	675.1
CCMC9			9		6.2	69	0.0004278	2337.5
CCMC18			18	Quenching	2.1	68	0.0001428	7002.8
CCMC27	250	2	27		2.1	48	0.0001008	9920.6
CCMC36			36		2.0	45	0.00009	11111.1
CCMC36-1			36	Cooling with air	4.5	61	0.0002745	3643.0
CCMC36-2	190	40	36	Quenching	3.6	63	0.0002268	4409.2

Table 1. Processing condition and electrical conductivity of the prepared CNT mat composites

Fig. 1. Weight residue of the CNT mat composites with respect to temperature. The weight fraction of the CNT mat incorporated into the composites was calculated from the figure.